

CALENDAR AND PHENOLOGICAL REGULARITIES OF SEASONAL MIGRATIONS OF BIRDS OF PREY IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract. *For the first time, it has been established that the migration of birds of prey from the Northern Hemisphere to the Southern Hemisphere or in the opposite direction occurs under the influence of patterns of increase and decrease in illumination along the meridians. According to the illumination level of grouped migrating birds of prey, spring arrival begins at an illumination level of $33 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $53 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $82 \cdot 10^4$ lux, and autumn departure ends at $30 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $55 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $80 \cdot 10^4$ lux. The degree of illumination at which the birds arrive is the same degree of illumination at which they depart.*

Keywords: *birds, calendar, illumination, meridians, migration, regularities, term.*

Introduction

Regular and consistent changes in the shape of Earth's orbit and the orientation of its axis of rotation create the Earth's annual cycle. The Sun measures days, seasons, and years for all living organisms. Solar and cosmic factors are the causes of the cyclicity of numerous ecological processes on Earth. As a result of adaptation to geophysical rhythms, animals and birds have developed similar biological daily, seasonal, and annual rhythms.

The Earth's equator is tilted at an angle of $23^{\circ}27'$ to its orbit. Consequently, the Sun illuminates and warms the Northern and Southern Hemispheres differently. At the same time of the year, different calendar days begin in the Northern and Southern Hemispheres. In the Northern Hemisphere, June 22 marks the start of summer calendar days and the longest day of the year. Conversely, in the Southern Hemisphere, winter calendar days begin. On December 22, the opposite occurs: winter starts in the Northern Hemisphere, and summer begins in the Southern Hemisphere. This tilt causes seasonal climate changes on Earth. Depending on the season, each geographic latitude experiences its unique duration of daylight and illumination. At the latitude of 40° , the differences in illumination between summer and winter are the most pronounced. During the winter half of the year, the total illumination decreases uniformly from south to north, while in the summer half, illumination decreases from north to south [1].

The cyclic nature of bird migrations and the timing of these migrations are influenced by both endogenous and exogenous factors. The annual cycle of seasonal phenomena in birds represents a system of genetically fixed processes that change in a regular pattern throughout the year.

There are certain phenological links between the progression of spring and the timing of migratory bird arrivals [25, 6]. Early in spring, when changes in nature favorable for birds (such as snowmelt and river thawing) are just beginning, favorable conditions arise for the arrival of short-distance migrants [8]. The northern boundaries of wintering areas for mallards, certain thrushes, and robins depend on winter isotherms and show a clear dependence on local conditions.

The speed at which migratory birds move from wintering grounds to nesting sites also follows specific patterns. Some birds, arriving later, move quickly to their nesting sites, while others advance slowly, seemingly following the progression of spring, gradually settling in their characteristic habitats day by day. Many scientists studying phenology have collected and analyzed long-term data on the spring migratory patterns of rooks, white storks, and cuckoos across European Russia [13, 19, 24]. The spring arrival of rooks generally progresses from the southwest to the northeast, with an

average speed of about 55 km per day. The movement of rooks is closely tied to air temperature but is not uniform, as lowland areas are populated earlier than uplands.

Observations have led to a concise conclusion: "No bird returns before its food appears." For instance, Cuckoos arrive no earlier than the overwintered silk moth caterpillars reach half their size and climb onto trees. Orioles return only when May beetles begin to fly. Warblers arrive when small, naked caterpillars of various leaf-rollers and inchworms grow. Swallows appear no earlier than the buzzing of at least some flies can be heard, and flycatchers return only when flying insects are present in large numbers. The timing of bird arrivals is undoubtedly linked to their feeding habits and the progression of spring, but migratory birds do not always appear at their summer habitats immediately after their characteristic food becomes available. Some species, such as the Yellow-breasted Bunting (*Emberiza aureola*), arrive very late, at the very end of spring, even though their food has long been abundant at their nesting sites [4, 23].

Thus, the position of the migration front depends not only on geographical features and the distribution of biologically suitable habitats but also on the preceding migration route and the location of wintering grounds [8, 5].

The autumn departure of birds is studied much less thoroughly than their spring arrival. The primary reason is the greater difficulty of observations. It is much easier to record the first appearance of a migratory bird in spring than to pinpoint the exact date of its last sighting in autumn. Birds appear less frequently in autumn phenological calendars than in spring ones, and the recorded dates are often imprecise. A remarkable feature of the autumn departure of many birds is the connection between their departure timing and their spring arrival. This was noted as early as 1853 by Russian ornithologist Kessler. Almost without exception, birds that arrive early in spring depart late in autumn, while those appearing very late in spring are among the first to leave, sometimes as early as late summer [14, 21, 10]. For most birds, daylight duration serves as a signaling factor, acting as one of the universally recognized cues that reliably indicate the time of year [2, 18, 15, 16]. Birds, like some other animals, exhibit highly developed light-based compass reactions closely linked to the functioning of their eyes. As demonstrated by [20], the daily rhythm of bird activity is largely determined by the diurnal changes in light intensity.

In strictly photoperiodic species, the length of the day and light levels regulate the timing and pace of development for spring migratory states (fat accumulation, gonad growth). Autumnal migratory states are governed by a long-term autonomous timing system initiated at the beginning of photoperiodic stimulation in spring [9].

Meteorological and phenological long-term observations have shown that the occurrence date of a given seasonal complex of phenomena deviates from the long-term average by no more than ± 7 days. Thus, the timing of a specific favorable period can be predicted with an accuracy of ± 7 days using calendars and long-term average data. If synchronization of the annual endogenous cycle with the astronomical calendar occurs throughout the preparatory period, the synchronization becomes most precise by the end of the period [7]. This highlights the clear advantage of aligning an individual's annual life cycle with the astronomical calendar.

The aim of this study is to investigate the ultimate signal that determines the beginning and end of birds' spring and autumn migrations.

The objective of the study is to examine natural warning signals as synchronizing factors for the start and end of migration during the spring and autumn periods.

1. Materials and methods

The study of the influence of environmental factors on migratory birds in the territory of Azerbaijan began in 2000 and continues to this day.

The light regime in the area is shaped by several factors: the primary astronomical factors, such as day length and the sun's altitude above the horizon, along with secondary factors, including cloud cover, the albedo of the underlying surface, and atmospheric transparency. The sun's altitude exhibits cyclic changes, cloud cover varies chaotically, and surface albedo changes seasonally.

Natural illumination on the Absheron Peninsula was measured using a Yu-116 luxmeter, with continuous registration conducted by devices developed by engineers from Moscow State University (Natural Illumination Recorder – NIR). The start and end dates of spring and autumn migrations for seven species of birds of prey were determined. A difference in total illumination between the summer and winter halves of the year ($2-3 \cdot 10^4$ lux) was identified. This difference is associated with cloudiness and other factors on migration days. The measurement error for natural illumination did not exceed 10–12%.

The timing of the start and end of spring and autumn migrations was compared with total illumination using the methodology outlined by [18]. The ranges of fluctuation and the table of total illumination for clear and cloudy skies were derived from [1]. By comparing long-term indicators [26, 11, 12] for the timing of spring and autumn migrations of mass bird species in northeastern Azerbaijan with our findings (2000–2024) across the republic, we confirmed that the start and end dates of spring and autumn migrations are consistent within a range of $\pm 1-5$ days. We completed the methodological work in the following sequence:

1.1. Each latitude receives the same day length and illumination for each half-year and depending on seasonality.

The Earth's equator is inclined to its orbital plane at an angle of $23^{\circ}27'$. As a result, the Sun alternately illuminates and warms the Northern and Southern Hemispheres. Consequently, corresponding seasons occur on different calendar dates in the two hemispheres, leading to seasonal climate variations across the globe. Depending on the season, each geographical latitude experiences its own characteristic day length and illumination level. Over the course of half a year, however, each latitude receives an equal total duration of daylight and illumination.

1.2. Lighting conditions are the most important synchronizer of daily and annual life rhythms.

Under natural conditions, the light regime—specifically, the ratio of day length to night length—serves as the most important synchronizing factor for the circadian and annual rhythms of physiological and behavioral activities.

1.3. The cyclical nature of seasonal bird movements, as well as the timing of their onset, are determined by endogenous and exogenous factors.

The rate of migration of birds from wintering grounds to breeding areas, and vice versa, across different latitudes follows distinct patterns. The cyclicity and timing of seasonal bird movements are determined by both endogenous and exogenous factors. The annual cycle of avian seasonal phenomena constitutes a system of genetically fixed processes that change regularly throughout the year.

1.4. The timing of seasonal migrations repeats within $\pm 4.8-7.7$ days.

The long-term dynamics of bird migration timing in the middle latitudes of Eastern Europe deviate from the multi-year average by no more than $\pm 4.8-7.7$ days. Differences in total illumination between the summer and winter half-years ($2-3 \times 10^4$ lx) are significantly influenced by cloud cover, surface albedo, atmospheric transparency, and other environmental factors occurring during migration periods.

1.5. Comparison of the beginning and end times of spring and autumn migration with illumination levels.

Long-term data on the onset and termination of spring and autumn migrations of Falconiformes were compared with corresponding illumination levels in Azerbaijan.

2. Results

By comparing long-term indicators of the start and end dates of spring and autumn migrations of Falconiformes with corresponding illumination levels, we identified three main groups of birds. Table 1.

Table 1. Periods of spring and autumn migrations of birds of prey (Falconiformes and Accipitriformes) at 40° Latitude and Illumination Levels

Species	Start and End of Spring Migration	Illumination During Spring Migration, 10^4 lx	Illumination During Autumn Migration, 10^4 lx	Start and End of Autumn Migration
Montagu's Harrier <i>Circus pygargus</i> Linn., 1758	18.II–7.IV	33–82	80–30	23.IX–16.XI
Western Marsh Harrier <i>Circus aeruginosus</i> Linn., 1758	20.III–2.IV	53–82	80–55	10.IX–12.X
Lesser Kestrel <i>Falco naumanni</i> Linn., 1758	25.III–5.IV	53–82	80–55	25.IX–30.X
White-tailed Eagle <i>Haliaeetus leucoryphus</i> Pall., 1771	7.IV–15.V	82–124	127–80	30.VIII–14.IX
Peregrine Falcon <i>Falco peregrinus</i> Tunst., 1771	13.III–9.IV	53–82	80–55	10.IX–31.X
Lanner Falcon <i>Falco biarmicus</i> Temm., 1825	18.III–2.IV	53–82	80–55	14.IX–16.X
Black Kite <i>Milvus migrans</i> Bodd., 1783	18.II–7.IV	33–82	80–30	23.IX–16.XI

1. To the first group: Comprising a single species, the Montagu's Harrier - *Circus pygargus* Linn., 1758; Black Kite (*Milvus migrans* Bodd., 1783), which begins migration from mid-February to April 7. Migration occurs at an illumination level of $33-82 \cdot 10^4$ lx.

2. Mid-spring group: Includes five species initiating migration in March and completing it in April, under an illumination range of $53-82 \cdot 10^4$ lx: Western Marsh Harrier *Circus aeruginosus* Linn., 1758. Lesser Kestrel (*Falco naumanni* Linn., 1758). Peregrine Falcon (*Falco peregrinus* Tunst., 1771); Lanner Falcon (*Falco biarmicus* Temm., 1825).

3. Late-spring group: White-tailed Eagle *Haliaeetus leucoryphus* Pall., 1771-is the sole species in this group, which begins spring migration in the first decade of April at an illumination level of $82 \cdot 10^4$ lx and ends in the second decade of May at $124 \cdot 10^4$ lx.

Autumn migration groups:

1. First Group: White-tailed Eagle *Haliaeetus leucoryphus* Pall., 1771; Includes the Autumn Migration: Begins in the last decade of August at an illumination level of $127 \cdot 10^4$ lx and ends in the second decade of September at $80 \cdot 10^4$ lx.

2. Mid-autumn group: Comprising five species that migrate from September to October at an illumination range of $80-55 \cdot 10^4$ lx: Lesser Kestrel *Falco naumanni* Linn., 1758: Western Marsh Harrier (*Circus aeruginosus* Linn., 1758); Peregrine Falcon (*Falco peregrinus* Tunst., 1771); Lanner Falcon (*Falco biarmicus* Temm., 1825).

3. Late-autumn group : Includes the Black Kite (*Milvus migrans* Bodd., 1783).

Autumn migration: Starts in the third decade of September and ends in the second decade of November at an illumination range of $80-30 \cdot 10^4$ lx.

Illumination patterns:

• **Spring migration:** Starts and ends with increasing illumination levels:

- Group 1: $33-82 \cdot 10^4$ lx
- Group 2: $53-82 \cdot 10^4$ lx
- Group 3: $82-124 \cdot 10^4$ lx

• **Autumn migration:** Starts and ends with decreasing illumination levels:

- Group 1: $127-80 \cdot 10^4$ lx
- Group 2: $80-55 \cdot 10^4$ lx
- Group 3: $80-30 \cdot 10^4$ lx

Correspondence in Illumination: The illumination level at the start of spring arrival corresponds to the level at the end of autumn departure:

Spring Arrival: $33 \cdot 10^4$ lx, $53 \cdot 10^4$ lx, $82 \cdot 10^4$ lx; Autumn Departure: $30 \cdot 10^4$ lx, $55 \cdot 10^4$ lx, $80 \cdot 10^4$ lx.

The illumination level at the end of spring arrival corresponds to the level at the start of autumn departure:

Spring End: $82 \cdot 10^4$ lx, $124 \cdot 10^4$ lx; Autumn Start: $80 \cdot 10^4$ lx, $127 \cdot 10^4$ lx

In Azerbaijan, spring migration begins and ends with increasing illumination in the summer mode at an illumination level from $33 \cdot 10^4$ lux to $124 \cdot 10^4$ lux. Autumn migration of birds begins and ends with decreasing illumination in the winter mode at an illumination level from $127 \cdot 10^4$ lux to $30 \cdot 10^4$ lux. According to the illumination level of grouped migrating birds of prey, spring arrival begins at an illumination level of $82 \cdot 10^4$ lux and ends at $124 \cdot 10^4$ lux, and autumn departure begins at an illumination level of $127 \cdot 10^4$ lux and ends at an illumination level of $80 \cdot 10^4$ lux. The degree of illumination at which arrival ends is the same degree of illumination at which departure of migrating birds begins.

Seasonal illumination difference: The observed difference in cumulative illumination between the summer and winter halves of the year ($2-3 \cdot 10^4$ lx) is influenced by cloud cover and other environmental factors during migration days.

4. Discussion

It is generally accepted that the cyclicity of migration is regulated by circadian (annual) rhythms that regulate the reproduction of birds. The cyclicity of migration and the reproduction period are regulated by environmental conditions, in the spring by photostimulation, and in other seasons by the length of the day [7, 21]. The day length factor determines the time and speed of sexual activity: the beginning and speed of spring migration: prepares birds for spring and autumn migration (the beginning and end of the molting period: the accumulation of fat, etc. [7].

The cyclic seasonal movement of birds, also periods of their offensive are connected with the exogenous and endogenous factors.

Annual cyclic rhythms are formed under the influence of ultimate factors [7, 21, 22]. Ultimate factors are those factors under the influence of which migration of birds has arisen. Such factors occur under the influence of natural selection and create a migratory situation in birds. As a second factor, a signal is considered, the change of which is not of great importance for the population. However, natural selection has used those signals as warning signals. As a result of the evolutionary process, the warning signal warns of the beginning of the activity of ultimate factors [15, 16].

Since the emergence of migration, both factors have created migratory situations in birds. The results show that for the ultimatum signal factor the birds use the length of the day and the illumination, as they have a strict annual cycle [7, 11]. The length of the day and the illuminations as a signal has a strict annual cyclicity, is accessible for perception by sight and correlated in its changes with the cycles of environmental conditions, is quite universal in all geographic latitudes and environmental situations [1, 17, 18].

5. Conclusion

For the first time, it has been established that the migration of raptors from the Northern to the Southern Hemisphere (and vice versa) occurs in accordance with regular patterns of increasing or decreasing illumination along meridians. The illumination level at which the spring arrival begins coincides with the illumination level at which the autumn departure of migratory birds of prey ends. According to the illumination level of grouped migrating birds of prey, spring arrival begins at an illumination level of $33 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $53 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $82 \cdot 10^4$ lux, and autumn departure ends at $30 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $55 \cdot 10^4$ lux; $80 \cdot 10^4$ lux. The degree of illumination at which the birds arrive is the same degree of illumination at which they depart.

Ethics:

Migratory birds were not used in the studies. The birds' spring migration and autumn migration were recorded.

AI Disclaimer

We did not use artificial intelligence technologies in the creation of this article.

Author Contributions

RB: data processing, formal analysis, methodology, writing – original draft; JSP: conceptualization, formal analysis, scientific supervision, writing – review and editing.

Both authors provided final approval for publication and agree to be accountable for the work performed.

Conflict of Interest Declaration

We declare no conflict of interest.

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